

Examining Decision-Making in Air Traffic Control: Enhancing Transparency and Decision Support Through Machine Learning, Explanation, and Visualization: A Case Study

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Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, eXplainable Artificial Intelligence, User-Centric XAI, Conflict Detection and Resolution, Air Traffic Management.

Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) has recently made significant advancements and is now pervasive across various application domains. This holds true for Air Transportation as well, where AI is increasingly involved in decision-making processes. While these algorithms are designed to assist users in their daily tasks, they still face challenges related to acceptance and trustworthiness. Users often harbor doubts about the decisions proposed by AI, and in some cases, they may even oppose them. This is primarily because AI-generated decisions are often opaque, non-intuitive, and incompatible with human reasoning. Moreover, when AI is deployed in safety-critical contexts like Air Traffic Management (ATM), the individual decisions generated by AI models must be highly reliable for human operators. Understanding the behavior of the model and providing explanations for its results are essential requirements in every life-critical domain. In this scope, this project aimed to enhance transparency and explainability in AI algorithms within the Air Traffic Management domain. This article presents the results of the project's validation conducted for a Conflict Detection and Resolution task involving 21 air traffic controllers (10 experts and 11 students) in En-Route position (i.e. high altitude flight management). Through a controlled study incorporating three levels of explanation, we offer initial insights into the impact of providing additional explanations alongside a conflict resolution algorithm to improve decision-making. At a high level, our findings indicate that providing explanations is not always necessary, and our project sheds light on potential research directions for education and training purposes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) experienced a significant resurgence during the 2010s, driven by increased ac-

cess to vast volumes of data and the discovery of the high computational efficiency of graphics card processors for accelerating machine learning algorithms (Council of Europe, 2020). This surge of interest in AI extended to every application domain, and Air Traffic Management (ATM) was no exception (Degas et al., 2022). However, despite numerous research efforts in applying AI to the ATM domain, its full operational integration and substantial benefits to end users have remained elusive. The slow progress in adopting AI in ATM can be attributed to the critical nature of

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this domain, where human lives are at stake, making safety the utmost priority.

Historically, safety in Air Traffic Management (ATM) has relied on human-in-the-loop systems (Di Flumeri et al., 2019), particularly air traffic controllers, and is likely to evolve towards the design of tightly human-centered systems. These systems must be comprehensible to end-users, adaptable to their mental and physical characteristics, and responsive to their psychological states. In various domains such as healthcare and criminal justice, the growing interest in AI to support high-stakes human decisions has driven the development of eXplainable AI (XAI). XAI, short for Explainable Artificial Intelligence, is a subfield of AI research dedicated to creating models and systems that offer understandable and interpretable explanations for their decisions and actions (Islam et al., 2022) (Wang et al., 2019). In the air traffic controller domain, XAI is essential as it ensures the transparency and reliability of AI systems, enabling controllers to trust and effectively collaborate with AI tools, ultimately enhancing safety and efficiency.

In Air Traffic Management (ATM), there is a growing interest in XAI methods and techniques that enable humans to understand: i) the AI algorithm (i.e., global explanation or interpretability), and ii) its solutions (i.e., local explanation or justification) (Degas et al., 2022). This interest has been manifested in various projects, and this article presents the results of one such project, the ARTIMATION project. This project investigates how transparency can be provided for different tasks in the ATM domain, taking both a model-centric and user-centric approach, with the aim of restoring the user's role in the data analytical process.

In preliminary work to identify the most promising tasks to address, as discussed in (Degas et al., 2022), the consortium conducted an analysis of the state of the art in AI and XAI for the ATM domain. They developed a taxonomy consisting of four categories (prediction, optimization, analysis, and modeling) that are closely aligned with AI in general and collectively define the objectives of the application:

- Prediction, paper seeking to foresee the future behaviour of a subject.
- Optimisation/Automation, papers seeking to enhance the behaviour of a subject.
- Analysis, papers seeking to understand the observed behaviour of a subject (Post-Analysis or Live).
- Modelling/Simulation, paper are modelling the behaviour of subject in order to simulate it.

From within those categories, three levels of explanation/transparency have been identified:

- **Description:** At the base level, Description provides an understanding of the AI system's attributes and inner workings, enabling users to grasp its fundamental characteristics.
- **Prediction:** Building upon Description, Prediction level allows users to anticipate the AI's outcomes, fostering a proactive approach to decision-making.
- **Prescription:** At the highest level, Prescription empowers users not only to predict but also to take corrective actions in response to potential AI errors or recommendations, ensuring safe and effective outcomes.

While these three levels can ensure safe and efficient AI-user collaboration, currently, we can only aim to address the descriptive level. This paper presents our initial attempt to provide such a descriptive level and assess its impact on air traffic controllers' understanding and acceptability.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the AI methods used, the techniques employed to enhance their explainability, section 3 the validation methodology. Section 4 describes the results of our validation. Finally, Section 5 provides a summary of our findings and concludes this study.

2 THE CONFLICT DETECTION AND RESOLUTION TOOL

Air Traffic Controllers (ATCOs) play a critical role in ensuring the safe and efficient movement of air traffic within controlled airspace (Mackay, 1999). Their primary responsibilities encompass traffic monitoring and conflict resolution, tasks that demand acute situational awareness and rapid decision-making. As guardians of the skies, ATCOs are entrusted with preventing collisions and maintaining orderly traffic flow. The nature of ATC work is inherently time-dependent, involving continuous monitoring of aircraft positions, altitudes, and trajectories (Letondal et al., 2013). This dynamic environment introduces stress and requires unwavering concentration from controllers. Recognizing the challenges posed by the complexity and pace of air traffic, there is a growing interest in incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) to assist ATCOs. AI has the potential to enhance the efficiency and safety of air traffic management by providing real-time analysis, predictive capabilities, and automated decision support (Hurter et al.,

2014). However, the integration of AI in the ATC domain must prioritize transparency. ATCOs rely on a deep understanding of the algorithms assisting them to establish trust, ensure reliability, and facilitate effective teamwork between humans and AI systems. A transparent level of explanation in AI algorithms is crucial for fostering collaboration and mitigating concerns related to the automation of critical tasks. This approach not only enhances the performance of AI-assisted air traffic management but also contributes to the overall trustworthiness of the system. As the aviation industry evolves, the careful balance between human expertise and AI assistance becomes paramount in achieving a seamless and secure air traffic control ecosystem.

In our paper, we delve into the investigation of conflict resolution algorithms within the context of air traffic control (ATC) due to the pivotal role these algorithms play in ensuring the safety and efficiency of airspace operations. As the complexity of air traffic continues to grow, understanding and refining these algorithms becomes paramount for addressing the evolving challenges faced by air traffic controllers, making it imperative to explore and enhance the mechanisms that underpin conflict resolution in this dynamic domain. Our Conflict Detection & Resolution task was performed using an Genetic Algorithm (Durand and Gotteland, 2006). The model was used to compute solutions of different conflicting scenarios, and the data produced by the Genetic Algorithm during the resolution process was used to build three model-centric visualisations.

2.1 Genetic Algorithm

In short, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) (Srinivas and Patnaik, 1994) describes a population and its evolutionary based on a Meta-Heuristic. This means that a GA tries to iteratively improve candidate solutions according to some predefined criteria (see Fig. 1). In our conflict resolution case, a candidate solution for the GA is a set of trajectories, some modified, some not. Candidate solutions forming the population are evaluated in function of three criteria: the duration of the conflicts, if any; the length of the trajectories; and the number of change of direction (i.e. order that must be given to implement this candidate solution). Once the GA has evaluated all candidate solution in the population, it selects a set of candidate solution, mostly the bests, but also other candidate solution to better explore the solution space. The algorithm then applies a set of mutation and crossover operations in an attempt to enhance the population and to possibly converge toward one of the optimal solutions (Durand

Figure 1: Evolution of the best candidate solution in function of the generation (i.e., iteration) for a conflict with 50 airplanes, from left to right: at the 250th, 500th, and 1000th generation. Taken from (Durand, 2004).

Figure 2: Blackbox visualization the solution proposed by the Genetic Algorithm. The air traffic control display offers a detailed visualization of aircraft dynamics. Current positions are represented by dynamic symbols, displaying real-time data on altitude and heading. The speed vector provides information on the aircraft’s current velocity.

and Gotteland, 2006).

2.2 Material of the Conflict Detection and Resolution Tool

As previously explained, our GA explored the possible solution for a given conflicting situation between aircraft and extracted one solution which is qualified as the “best” one with the given optimization criteria (number of actions, length of the trajectory, and number of orders). In order to provide explanation for the proposed solution, we developed three different type of data presentation which are detailed in the following.

Black box (BB): This visualization is as simple as possible and only displays the proposed solution by the GA algorithm, enhanced by instructions to proceed (see Figure 2): Airplane trajectories are colored differently. The minimal distance between airplanes is computed and displayed in yellow. The control orders that must be given by the ATCO to the different airplanes are placed along the trajectory, as well

Figure 3: Heatmap visualization the solution proposed by the Genetic Algorithm. Green areas show the contour of possible solutions, while the red area shows the location of conflicting trajectories.

as their ordering (1st, 2nd ...). This data presentation is not an explanation by itself but the simple data presentation of the “best” solution the GA algorithm managed to extract. Compared to existing system, the Black Box data representation directly provide a solution to a detected conflict, while the system currently used only displays the detected conflicting aircraft without further information to solve it.

Heat map (HM): To better explain the reasoning behind the proposed solution was made, we decided to show on top of the proposed solution what was explored by the GA, and if whether it was good or bad. To do so, we created heatmaps of the explored trajectories showing how aircrafts trajectories can safely be modified. In Figure 3, the operator can see that: AFR3218 can only follow its trajectory or go to the left (most probably it is less efficient and not required). KLM1258 and EZY208 cannot follow their trajectories and need to turn left (only possibility). In addition, users can see how much they can wait to turn each airplane, by seeing the end of the “safe zone” (green area) and the begin of the “dangerous zone” (red area). Such data representation is generated with the cumulative view of good and bad solutions. Each solution is convoluted with a gaussian kernel and then accumulated into a density map. Such technique helps do visually define areas also called contour maps (Scheepens et al., 2011).

Storytelling (SB): To better explain the proposed solution, the final visualization, called the Storyboard, depicts a timeline of events detailing the application of measures to resolve the conflicting situation in aircraft (See Figure 4). Possibly and alternate solution, showing that other solutions can be made, but are less efficient. Limit solution, showing what needs to be

done if the solution is not implemented right away to avoid any conflict. We use existing Data Driven Storytelling technique with step-based explanations and counterfactual explanations (Riche et al., 2018).

2.3 Methods of the Conflict Detection and Resolution Tool (CD&R)

In total, 21 participants were recruited to participate our validation sessions. The validation platform is presented in Figure 5. Participants were recruited targeting two populations, “Expert” and “Student”. For the experts, 11 were recruited (3 female (27%), 8 male (73%), mean age of 41 years (ranging between 34-51 years old)). The population was mostly composed of ATCO instructors (7), former ATCO now in research (2), and former ATCO now in ATCO formation (2). For the students, 10 were recruited (4 female (40%), 6 male (60%), Mean age of 22 years old (ranging between 20-26 years old)) in the oldest formation available at their training center, just before they left its premises to their affected in a Control Center.

10 validation Scenarios were created for the validation procedure. This simulation scenario was created using a 2016 traffic record, in a fictitious sector created by a training center for ATCO formation. The record was modified to create the conflict required for the validation. The conflict was designed to create different workload and difficulty of resolution, simplified in two categories “Easy” and “Hard” by adding aircrafts in the conflict—either following, or converging—or by modifying the contextual traffic. Our different levels of difficulty were verified with 3 ATCOs, collecting their feelings about the scenario complexity to solve every conflict.

The validation procedure of the CD&R tool was designed to 1) primary tests the different level of explainability (Blackbox, Heatmap, Storyboard), while 2) decreasing as much as possible any risk of bias, 3) maximizing the quality of neurophysiological measures, and 4) keeping the experiment short enough.

As such, every scenario of conflict was following 4 different steps: 1) video of the simulation with the conflict that has to be solved and the surrounding contextual aircrafts (45s), to gain situational awareness, and emulate the classical work environment; 2) displaying one type of explanation (Blackbox, Heatmap, Storyboard) during a fixed time (60s), with the possibility to go to the next phase after 30s, to avoid boredom and disengagement; 3) ask the user to draw the solution it want to give after seeing the solution proposed; 4) answer questionnaires.

Every level of explanation was tested with three different scenarios. The first scenario was used as a

Figure 4: Storyboard presentation of the proposed solution. The sequence of images 1 to 3 shows the temporal steps to solve the conflict. The limit solution shows the good solution but with is close the minimum separation criteria between conflicting aircraft.

warmup, and the two others where the one data was gathered for analysis (while still gathering data on the first one, as control data). To avoid any bias linked to the order of presentation, fatigue, or scenario, we used a latin square to mix scenarios with level of explanation, and the order of presentation of the different level of explanation.

The number of scenarios presented was decided in such way that the total experiment—from briefing, setting neurophysiological sensors, testing each level of explanation, and final debriefing, was not exceeding 2h.

During this simulation phase, we administered two different questionnaires in two different times. After each scenario, participants were given a self-report ad-hoc questionnaire

- Understanding (two Likert Scales from 1 to 5): 1) understanding the proposed solution, and 2) why it had been generated
- Agreement with the solution (Dicotomial "Yes/No")

To have a more detailed categorization, we separated each category (BB - Black Box; HM - Heat Map; SB - StoryBoard) in two different complexity levels depending on the scenario (E - Easy; H - Hard). Then, after each condition, participants were given another questionnaire made up of Likert Scales from 1 to 5, in order to assess:

- The usability of the decision support system, divided into 3 items (The ease to learn to operate the tool, the clarity and understandability of the tool, and its ease to use) (Bicchi and Pallottino, 2000).
- The trust on the solution (Hidalgo et al., 2021).
- The situational awareness when using the tool (Endsley and Jones, 2013).
- The acceptability of the tool, with two items (The will to use the tool in the future, and the appreciation of the interface) (Chiarella et al., 2022),

- The impact on work performance, with 4 items (Decrease of conflict solving; Increase accuracy solving conflict; Increase in work performance; Ease to work) (Isaac and Ruitenber, 2017).

3 QUANTITATIVE DATA - QUESTIONNAIRES AND NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL MEASURES

The results presented below derived from quantitative self-report measurements, such as ad-hoc questionnaires (post-run and post-condition), and qualitative assessments, meaning debriefings with the participants. The statistical analyses have been performed using Jamovi 2.2.5 (The Jamovi Project, 2023 <https://www.jamovi.org/>), and have been matched with the neurophysiological measurements to assess the impact of the 3 proposed visualisations on the Acceptance of the ATCO (split up into the constructs of Understanding, Agreement and Acceptability), and on the Human Performance (composed by stress, workload, situation awareness, usability, trust, task performance). Moreover, a correlation between acceptance and human performance has been performed. Final qualitative considerations regarding the system performance from the safety and extended impact on ATM system point of view were gathered. The participants were placed in ACHIL En-Route control setting, our simulation facilities. The control screen was either displaying the simulation, the solution and level of explanation, the drawing, or the survey. Prior to the experiment, they were placed the neurophysiological sensors, a Electro Dermal Activity (EDA) recording device (shimmer sensing) and an electroencephalography (EEG) headset (<https://www.mindtooth-eeg.com> Mindtooth), both linked to a Tablet embedding the Mindtooth recording suite,

Table 1: Post-scenario questionnaire results.

Item	Average Score					
	E-BB ^a	Easy E-HM ^b	E-SB ^c	H-BB ^d	Hard H-HM ^e	H-SB ^f
(Un1) “The solution was easy to understand”	4.56	3.67	3.56	3.89	3.11	3.11
		3.93			3.37	
(Un2) “I understand why the proposed solution has been generated”	4.33	4.33	4.22	3.44	3.44	3.44
		4.3			3.44	

^aEasy-Black Box, ^bE-Heat Map, ^cEasy-Storyboard, ^dHard-Black Box, ^eHard-Heat Map, ^fHard-Storyboard

Table 2: Post-condition questionnaire results.

Category	Item	Score		
		BB ^a	HM ^b	SB ^c
Usability	(Us1) ”Learn to operate the tool would be easy for me”	4.11	3.56	2.78
	(Us2) “I find the tool clear and understandable”	3.67	3.22	2.56
	(Us3) “I find the tool easy to use”	3.56	3.56	3.33
Trust	(T1) “I felt confident when using the tool”	2.89	3.22	3.11
Situation Awareness	(SA1) “The tool improved my Situation Awareness of the conflict presented”	3	3.11	3.22
Acceptability	(A1) “I would like to use this tool in the future”	3.22	2.23	2.78
	(A2) “I like the new decision support interface”	3.78	2.67	2.22
Work Performance	(Wp1) ”Using this tool in my job would allow me to solve conflicts faster”	3.22	3.11	2.89
	(Wp2) “Using this tool in my job would increase my accuracy in solving conflicts”	3.44	3.22	3.11
	(Wp3) “Using this tool would improve my work performance”	3.33	2.78	2.89
	(Wp4) “Using this tool would make my work easier”	3.56	3.11	3.52

^aBlack Box, ^bHeat Map, ^cStoryboard

allowing a synchronized recording of both the signals, and to put specific markers used for the following off-line analysis. In particular, the recorded EEG signal has been used to derive the approach-withdrawal neurometric, related to the level of acceptance experienced by the user in front of a specific operational solution. It has been calculated by the difference between the EEG alpha activity over the frontal right sites, and the EEG alpha activity over the frontal left sites (Di Flumeri et al., 2017; Giorgi et al., 2021; Borghini et al., 2017).

3.1 Self-Report Questionnaires

All the following data are expected to be framed in Likert Scale from 1 to 5 values, 1 meaning “strongly disagree”, 3 meaning “Neither agree or disagree”, and

5 meaning “strongly agree”. Understanding (i.e., how much the provided explanation is clear and understandable by the ATCO). In terms of understanding of how the advisory was generated, there were no significant differences between conditions for the experts, with average scores showing they still understood the AI outcome (BB:4.0; HM:3.5; SB:3.2). Students reported a slightly higher understanding of the resolution generation in the BB condition (BB: 4.4; HM: 4.1; SB: 3.7). A significant positive correlation between the two items of understanding has been found. Therefore, the two items have been aggregated to ease analyses. To assess the differences between the three levels of visual explainability, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) test has been conducted for the understanding variable. After a post-hoc comparison between the three levels, the BB condition resulted

Figure 5: Validation setup for Neurophysiological Measures.

in a more understood AI outcome by all the sample than the Storyboard (SB) condition ($p = 0.030$). Moreover, the post-hoc comparison between the expertise level of the participants showed a significant difference in understanding between students and experts, resulting in the student group having a higher understanding of the solution ($p = 0.018$). No other significant differences were found. Agreement (i.e., the state for which a participant agrees with a specific solution provided by the AI). In general, experts were accepting/agreeing with the proposed AI resolution less frequently. In particular, in the Heat Map (HM) condition the students reported a clearly higher level or agreement compared with experts (Students = 90). Acceptability (i.e., the intention to accept a new technology, the perceived usefulness and intuitive usability in the technology other than having favourable attitudes to adopt it, and the individual's feelings, favourable or unfavourable, about particular aspects of the environment or objects related to the environment). A significant correlation between the 2 acceptability items ("I would like to use this tool in the future", "I like the new decision support interface") has been found. Therefore, the two acceptability items have been merged. For the acceptability items, a post-hoc comparison between the three conditions has been conducted. The BB condition resulted being

significantly more acceptable than both the HM ($p = 0.033$) and the SB ($p < 0.001$). No significant differences in the interaction between the condition and the complexity of the scenarios has been found. To assess the difference in the acceptability items between the expertise and between conditions, an ANOVA test has been conducted. After a post-hoc comparison, a significant effect of the expertise on the acceptability of the visual explanation has been found: the students found the interfaces globally more acceptable than the experts ($p < 0.001$). A post-hoc comparison assessing the interaction between the expertise level and the condition has been conducted. All the explainability conditions resulted significantly more acceptable for the students than for the experts. The black box was significantly more acceptable for students than for the experts ($p = 0.020$), as for the heat map condition ($p < 0.001$) and for the Storyboard as well ($p = 0.001$). Between the experts, the black box condition resulted being significantly more acceptable than both the heat map ($p = 0.021$) and the storyboard ($p = 0.002$). In the expert group, no significant differences between the heat map and the storyboard condition have been found. Between the students, no significant differences between conditions have been found. Situational Awareness (i.e., the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and a projection of their status soon) (Endsley, 1995). An ANOVA has been conducted for the Situational Awareness items, followed by a post-hoc comparison. A significant difference between students and experts has been found on the Situational Awareness items, resulting in students having an improvement of situational awareness significantly higher than the experts ($p < 0.001$). For the Heat Map condition, students resulted having a significantly higher improvement in situational awareness than experts ($p = 0.023$). Usability (i.e., quality attribute assessing how easy user interfaces are to use and describing the easiness a system allows a user to get to a specific goal). An ANOVA has been conducted for the items of usability. After a post-hoc comparison of the results of the questionnaires for the usability items, in the whole sample, the black box resulted significantly more usable than the storyboard condition ($p = 0.049$). At the same time, globally, the students reported a significantly higher usability of all the tools than the experts ($p < 0.001$). Between the experts' group, the black box condition resulted being significantly more usable than the storyboard ($p < 0.001$). No other significant differences have been found. Trust (i.e., a cognitive state usually influencing the actual, behavioural dependence on automation. The operator's use of

automation is related to his or her momentary trust, which in turn is related to the type and frequency of faults and operators' confidence in their own ability). To assess the differences between the condition and the expertise level of the sample for the trust items, an ANOVA has been conducted. After a post-hoc comparison, a significant difference between students and experts has been found: students had a significantly higher trust in the presented resolution advisory than the experts ($p = 0.009$). No significant differences between conditions have been observed. Task performance (i.e., the effectiveness with which job incumbents carry out activities that contribute to the organization's "technical core" either directly by executing a part of its technical process or indirectly by providing it with needed materials or services). The 4 items composing the work performance index has been merged after a positive significant correlation between the items has been found. The post-hoc comparison done after the ANOVA shows how students reported a higher improved perceived work performance independently on the conditions ($p < 0.001$). Between the two groups, students reported a significantly more improved work performance than the experts ($p = 0.032$). The same result has been found for the heat map condition ($p = 0.048$) and the storyboard condition ($p = 0.046$). A correlation matrix to understand if the items of the sub-constructs were measuring the human performance and the acceptance was performed between all the sample. A significant correlation between the items has been found, therefore, the items were merged to assess the correlation between the acceptance and the human performance. After performing a correlation matrix between the acceptance and the human performance, a significant correlation has been found: the human performance while interacting with the XAI tools is correlated to the acceptance of the solutions provided by the Artificial Intelligence ($p < 0.001$). Therefore, we tried to assess the correlation between the acceptance and the human performance splitting the sample in experts and students. In both the experimental groups a significant correlation ($p < 0.001$ in both cases) between the acceptance and the human performance has been found.

3.2 Neurophysiological Results

A repeated measures ANOVA ($CI=0.95$) has been performed, by considering the two factors (i.e., conditions [Black Box; Heat Map; Storyboard] and repetitions [1st and 2nd]). The statistics has been performed for each experimental group (i.e., students and experts), to highlight any different.

Figure 6: Post-condition questionnaire 'Q: I would like to use this tool in the future' N=21.

Figure 7: Error bars showing for each experimental group (i.e. students and experts) the difference in approach-withdrawal index among the three experimental conditions.

The results showed a different behaviour between students and experts. In particular, the students exhibited the highest approach-withdrawal on the HM solution, with respect to the other two conditions (higher than BB solution, $p = 0.1$; higher than SB, $p = 0.07$). Otherwise, experts experienced a higher approach-withdrawal in correspondence of the SB solution, that was higher (trend, $p = 0.088$) than the BB condition. In detail, students exhibited the highest approach-withdrawal (acceptability) on the HM solution. From the debriefings it was clear that student's acceptability from the HM solution was higher when compared to experts. They mentioned that it was visually appealing, interesting and the use of colour was appreciated. Another thing that was appreciated was that it gives them more flexibility and does not point them towards a single resolution, they can analyse and come up with their own solution, but this could become critical in terms of an overall high workload scenario. The task that participants were performing in this experiment focused on the resolution of single conflicts, but it does not correspond to the overall role of an En route ATCO, so the results also might have been affected by the fact that it was focused on a single task and therefore the analysis should take this inconsideration. The task that participants were performing in this experiment focused on the resolution of single conflicts, but it does not correspond to the overall role of an En route ATCO, so the results also might have been affected by the fact that it

was focused on a single task and therefore the analysis should take this inconsideration. Experts experienced a higher approach-withdrawal (acceptability) towards the SB solution, which was higher (trend) than the black-box. Here the differences between conditions were not significant but they are just a trend. Both in questionnaires ratings and in the debriefings experts mentioned their preference towards the BB solution, they were that it was more straight forward, easy to understand and mainly it allowed them to make their decision in less time compared to the heat map (HM) or the storyboard (SB) solution. One possible explanation for this discrepancy between results of experts could be related to the intrinsic bias induced by the BB condition, especially on experts, that are of course experienced and used to face with this kind of solutions, with respect to the other two conditions, that, despite the training, were still new. The approach-withdrawal index is able to catch intrinsic (and instantaneous) reactions coming from the user brain, that are not by definition biased the experience, or by the long thinking regarding the possible operational use of this solution (that is instead measured by questionnaire post experiment). In other words, the instinct and instantaneous reaction, suggest that the storyboard (and on average also the HM, but not significantly) could potentially be well accepted by the operators, even more with respect to the BB, but the long thinking of operators, suggests instead a possible lack in effectiveness (Di Flumeri et al., 2017; Giorgi et al., 2021; Borghini et al., 2017). During the debriefings, when asked about their preference 11/11 ATCOs reported that they preferred the Black box (BB) solution, even if one of them also liked the concept of the Heat map (HM). The main reasons for the BB preference were that it was more straight forward, easy to understand and mainly it allowed them to make their decision in less time compared to the heat map (HM) or the storyboard (SB) solution. The students that preferred the HM mentioned the fact that it was visually appealing, interesting and the use of colour was appreciated. Participants that preferred also mentioned that it gives them more flexibility, because they can analyse and come up with their own solution. On the downside it takes more time to analyse in more complex conflicts or conflict with aircraft and that makes it less suitable in situations in which the ATCO would need to make a fast decision.

3.3 Qualitative Data - Semi-Structured Interviews

Acceptance. During the debriefings, students generally favoured the HM visualization modality, citing its

visual appeal as their preferred resolution visualization condition. Experts, on the other hand, were hesitant to accept solutions not of their own creation, fearing potential time loss in understanding tool proposals and the risk of being "out of the loop." Experienced ATCOs noted that their strategies, not considered in the algorithm, involved intervening in multiple conflicts to avoid penalizing one flight too heavily. They expressed uncertainty about the ML algorithm's parameters for generating visual conflict resolution proposals. The Genetic algorithm tended to propose interventions in fewer aircraft. Some participants mentioned a lack of time to analyze and integrate AI solution proposals. Regarding future tool use, students showed interest in the BB and HM conditions despite reported improvement needs, with preferences split (6/10 for BB, 3/10 for HM, 1/10 for SB). Experts, however, expressed a neutral stance on the BB condition and disagreed on using the HM and SB tools, unanimously favoring the BB condition during debriefings. Human Performance. During the debriefings, both experts and students mentioned that the BB solution configured as the less disruptive since it followed a similar approach to most implemented en-route tools and elements that the ATCOs are familiar with. Most of the participants mentioned that it was clear, logical and did not clutter other information on the screen (did not conceal other information). They also mentioned that it was useful to know the turning point of aircraft in the trajectory. The fact that it provided a single resolution solution was appreciated in conflicts that are more complex, also if they involve more than two aircraft. Students were the ones that highlighted the following benefits of the HM solution. They pointed out that the visual component as an advantage and that they could see which trajectories would be conflicting or not. This visualisation provides also room for other operational factors that might not be computed by the algorithm like bad weather (turbulence). ATCOs can easily trace the zones where the plane can pass in advance. One ATCO mentioned the projection of the envelope was easier to remember than just a number of degrees that the BB solution provides, but the level experience probably influences this opinion. In general, participants mentioned that they would prefer to have access to the tools on demand because they were considered more useful in complex scenarios or scenario in which they would be experiencing a high level of workload. Trust. Experts reportedly were not confident when using any of the solutions, but this might have been impacted by the fact that they had limited training and explanation. Some ATCOs, especially professional ATCOs, mentioned that they felt

they would need more information and training on how the Machine Learning (ML) algorithm in order to trust it. ATCOs mentioned that trust in the solutions is a requirement to use them in operations. That trust must be acquired before or after operational usage, either in training, with briefing or even during debriefings. Therefore, we can say that explainability might be more relevant for applications for those purposes. Task performance. During debriefings ATCO students mentioned how the BB solution possible advantages solving conflicts in a faster way. System performance. Safety. ATCOs mentioned that the HM solution's current design can impact safety by cluttering and masking important information on the radar. The SB concept in terms of implementation was related to the fact that the amount of information is not calibrated for the type of En route task, so the time the information takes to be analysed could create cognitive tunnelling situations. More generally in terms of XAI applications for conflict detection and resolution tools, there could be a higher risk for ATCOs to implement suggestions without checking what has been (once the ATCO trust the tools). On the long run relying on the tool could lowering ATCO the vigilance and loose skills overtime. But of course, these tool implementations would have to be followed by new training requirements to mitigate the negative effect on performance that were just mentioned. Most of the ATCOs mentioned that they find the solutions proposed by the system were good but if they are not matching their solution, it forces the ATCO to think twice or ultimately doubt his own solution. One ATCO complemented that he would be reluctant to accept a solution that is not his own simply because he might find himself in a situation that he does not feel that he can rapidly recover, because at that point he might be 'out of the loop'. The participants that mentioned more frequently that the proposed solution was making them doubt their own solutions were students when the solutions was not matching their own. This could point us in the direction of the importance of the solutions conformance to the ATCOs strategies and the impact on their acceptance and ultimately, safety. The fact that the proposed solution is not matching the solution of the ATCO could ultimately make him loose more time analysing or worse, make them fall behind what is going on in their sector. AI support and types of conflicts Most participants felt that the AI solutions proposed were not useful for conflicts with two aircraft. They thought that the BB solution could be useful in conflicts involving three or more conflicts. On the other hand, the visualisation conditions with more 'explainability' embedded, HM and SB correspondingly, based on most debriefings were

considered less useful for more complex operational scenarios, in short, less operationally acceptable. ATCOs felt that in more complex scenarios or when they are experiencing more workload, they could be more willing to accept the solutions proposed by the tool. In general, students and experts faced the AI decision support in conflict resolution in two different ways based on their feedback in debriefings. The experts seem to tend to consistently compare the AI solution with their own, assuming their solution is the best to be surpassed by the AI proposal. On the other hand, students put on the same level both their own solution and the AI proposal, being more open to accept a proposal that they did not come up with (higher levels of trust). XAI application in ATM. Most ATCOs mentioned that if they would need more time to analyse and double check the proposals from the solution with explainable AI solutions they tested and that could ultimately translate in an increased workload during operations and/or possible loss of situational awareness due cognitive tunnelling while using the tools. This seem to point out that higher explainability could be more useful for less timely critical or tasks or operational phases in which the ATCOs are subject to lower risk of cognitive workload, like planning tasks. Training. Some ATCOs mentioned that it would be interesting to explore and better understand the advantages of the AI solutions for training. The main focus could be on understanding how experts (maybe with different approaches or goals) would solve or work in certain scenarios. To make them visualize trajectories and different approaches based on different parameters could be very useful is to discuss and debrief. During the debriefings and final discussion there was not a univocal opinion on which solutions that would be preferred for training uses. Each ATCO seemed to have their own preference. What emerged was that all solutions and AI in general were perceived as having potential for training. The higher the visual XAI the better for training, because they elicit better the reasons behind the proposed conflict detection and on the resolution itself. Participants even mentioned that they could see the solutions with higher XAI visualisation to have potential to be used during trainings with AI tools and once the trainees see how the ML algorithm works and to build trust, with the support of these solutions, they can start using the tools with less visual XAI for the actual operations. Two ATCOs alerted to the fact that using AI tools to learn in conflict solving scenarios too early in the training process could have drawbacks, since ATCOs could end up mimicking the AI tools work strategy before developing their own. Personalization of ML algorithms and ATCO strategies. During the debriefings

some ATCOs voiced their interest in the use of applications of AI and ML algorithms to learn strategies from them. ATCO 18 reports “I think it would be interesting if, when you arrive at the position, you have a sort of profile of how you control it and the AI adapts to each person, which would be amazing, but I guess it would be something for the future.”. Kirwan, Flynn, & Flynn (Kirwan et al., 2001) studied controllers across seven nations, and found general agreement across controllers on the factors, rules, and principles they used to devise en route resolution strategies. Strategies were defined by four main dimensions:

- Formal rules—such as Letters of Agreement, or the semi-circular rule;
- Principles—such as ‘minimise number of aircraft to move,’ or ‘solve easy conflicts first’;
- Contextual factors—such as aircraft type, destination, distance to go; and
- ‘No-No’s’— control strategies, eleven in total, that controllers will never use in conflict resolution. Examples include “never use speed as a resolution mechanism,” or “never leave conflict aircraft not locked on heading.”

Westin (Westin, 2017) reviewed the MUFASA project’s exploration of controller resolution strategies both within- and across controllers, for reasons of developing advisory automation. Using a classification framework (i.e., resolution type/direction/degree etc), it was shown that intra-controller agreement (i.e. consistency) was higher than inter-controller agreement, and that inter-controller agreement was lower for specific manoeuvre choices. Having a ML algorithm that learns ‘Principles’ and ‘Control strategies’ context based on a single ATCO or to a wider category based on ATCO control strategies type would be a way forward to improve AI support based on ATCOs feedback.

4 LESSON LEARNED

What was shown in our project was that it is possible to open black-boxes and explain AI models in ATM domains. The lesson learned from the validation outcomes are summarized in the following.

XAI - Negative Effects: XAI / Transparency might have negative effects on performance and acceptability in conflict resolution tasks. Most ATCOs mentioned that if they would need more time to analyse and double check the proposals with higher XAI and

that could ultimately translate in an increased workload during operations and/or in the worst case causing cognitive tunnelling while using the tools.

XAI - Temporal Constraint: XAI/Transparency should be applied in operational phases that are not so timely constrained. In the end, for time pressured task, we would recommend not giving explanations as it adds workload to the ATCOs as they compare their solutions with the one given. Instead, having visuals that ease the creation of a mental model to solve the problem would be recommended. This doesn’t exclude adding transparency to the system that will be used in operational phase that are timely constrained. Transparency will still be useful in post-operation to understand unexpected behaviour, in integration or tool development to verify the behaviour of the AI system, or in training with the operators to gain trust in the system. We recommend just to not use it when a decision needs to be taken in a very short amount of time.

XAI - Parameters: The parameters that are used to train the algorithms should be carefully selected because they can introduce bias in the AI /proposals. Any multi-criteria optimising system will introduce some bias if the criteria are truly independent. Proposing different solution considering different parameters could be a solution, conforming the behaviour of the system to the operator behaviour could also be one.

XAI - Acceptability: Conformal AI solutions have the potential to achieve higher acceptance from ATCOs. More conformal decision aids, meaning aids that are closer to individual problem-solving styles, can improve acceptance. On a final note, participants voiced their interest in the use of applications of AI and ML algorithms to learn strategies from them.

AI Teaming: Transparency could support humans in building Trust in AI tools. Trust in the solutions or tools that involve AI is a requirement to use it in operations, there should be no surprises. ATCOs while dealing with these tools and they should know how the tools work, how the ML algorithms are learning, and which type of variables are used while learning and they should know the limitations of those same tools. Our results highlighted those participants during the CD&R visualisation tools experiment agreed that trust in these tools has to be acquired before or right after operational usage, meaning as training, with briefing or even during debriefing tools. Therefore, XAI can potentially be more important during

those phases and not during the operational use of AI tools.

Innovation in ATM: Less trained ATCOs might be more willing to adopt new tools and innovative HMIs. ATCO experts are biased toward using the tool they are used to have. One working several years with the same tools require a lot of time to work with new tools and accept them. Simple training in a validation process will hardly correct this bias. As such, having experienced and less experienced participants during the validation is important take this bias into account.

Critical Domain: Using optimal tools and explanations of the tools during training could be beneficial. Based on previous lessons, we can hypothesize that using Explainable AI for training purposes can be helpful in safety-critical and time-pressured tasks in creating a different mental model of the conflict, having the opportunity to be trained both in elaborating a functional solution and comparing it to an optimal one.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper reports several positive outcomes, notably emphasizing the importance of trust-building in air traffic control through Explainable AI (XAI) and transparency. These elements played a pivotal role in encouraging the acceptance of AI tools in operational settings. During less time-constrained operational phases, the integration of XAI and transparency mechanisms not only enhanced understanding but also contributed to more efficient decision-making processes among ATCOs. Additionally, the careful selection of AI algorithm parameters was highlighted as a valuable practice for mitigating bias, ensuring fair and accurate decision-making. Personalized, conformal decision aids tailored to individual problem-solving styles were well-received, leading to increased acceptance and user satisfaction among ATCOs. Furthermore, the introduction of AI explainability during training phases was deemed transformative, boosting ATCOs' confidence and competence, particularly in safety-critical and time-sensitive tasks. This reflects a positive outlook for the future of AI in air traffic management, characterized by trust, efficiency, fairness, and innovation. In summary, the ARTIMATION project not only demonstrated the feasibility of XAI in ATM but also revealed a series of positive outcomes, ranging from improved trust and performance to bias mitigation and innovation support. These find-

ings pave the way for a more efficient, adaptable, and user-friendly future in air traffic management.

While ARTIMATION marked a significant starting point in unraveling the potential of Explainable AI (XAI) in air traffic control (ATC), it has become evident that further exploration is essential to fully comprehend how XAI could benefit the field. This realization has paved the way for future work in the form of the TRUSTY project, which represents the next phase in advancing our understanding and application of XAI within ATC. TRUSTY is envisioned as a promising continuation of this journey. Its primary mission, in the context of forthcoming efforts, is to harness the capabilities of artificial intelligence (AI) to bolster efficiency and enhance safety in the global deployment of Remote Digital Towers (RDT). Building upon the foundation laid by ARTIMATION, TRUSTY will place a heightened focus on transparency and trustworthiness in the decision-making processes of AI systems operating within the complex context of RDT.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was financed by the European Union's Horizon 2020 within the framework SESAR 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement N. 894238, project Transparent artificial intelligence and automation to air traffic management systems, ARTIMATION and N. 101114838, Trustworthy intelligent system for remote digital tower, TRUSTY, HORIZON-SESAR-2022-DES-ER-01.

REFERENCES

- Bicchi, A. and Pallottino, L. (2000). On optimal cooperative conflict resolution for air traffic management systems. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 1(4):221–231.
- Borghini, G., Aricò, P., Di Flumeri, G., Sciaraffa, N., Colosimo, A., Herrero, M.-T., Bezerianos, A., Thakor, N. V., and Babiloni, F. (2017). A new perspective for the training assessment: Machine learning-based neuro-metric for augmented user's evaluation. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 11.
- Chiarella, S. G., Torromino, G., Gagliardi, D. M., Rossi, D., Babiloni, F., and Cartocci, G. (2022). Investigating the negative bias towards artificial intelligence: Effects of prior assignment of ai-authorship on the aesthetic appreciation of abstract paintings. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 137:107406.
- Council of Europe (2020). History of artificial intelligence.

- Degas, A., Islam, M. R., Hurter, C., Barua, S., Rahman, H., Poudel, M., Ruscio, D., Ahmed, M. U., Begum, S., Rahman, M. A., Bonelli, S., Cartocci, G., Di Flumeri, G., Borghini, G., Babiloni, F., and Aricó, P. (2022). A survey on artificial intelligence (ai) and explainable ai in air traffic management: Current trends and development with future research trajectory. *Applied Sciences*, 12(3).
- Di Flumeri, G., Aricó, P., Borghini, G., Sciaraffa, N., Maglione, A. G., Rossi, D., Modica, E., Trettel, A., Babiloni, F., Colosimo, A., and Herrero, M. T. (2017). Eeg-based approach-withdrawal index for the pleasantness evaluation during taste experience in realistic settings. In *2017 39th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*, pages 3228–3231.
- Di Flumeri, G., De Crescenzo, F., Berberian, B., Ohneiser, O., Kramer, J., Aricó, P., Borghini, G., Babiloni, F., Bagassi, S., and Piastra, S. (2019). Brain-computer interface-based adaptive automation to prevent out-of-the-loop phenomenon in air traffic controllers dealing with highly automated systems. *Frontiers in human neuroscience*, 13:296.
- Durand, N. (2004). *Algorithmes Génétiques et autres méthodes d'optimisation appliqués à la gestion de trafic aérien*. Habilitation à diriger des recherches, INPT.
- Durand, N. and Gotteland, J.-B. (2006). Genetic Algorithms Applied to Air Traffic Management. In *Metaheuristics for Hard Optimization Methods and Case Studies*, volume Chapter 9, pages pp 277–306. Springer.
- Endsley, M. R. (1995). Toward a theory of situation awareness in dynamic systems. *Human factors*, 37(1):32–64.
- Endsley, M. R. and Jones, W. (2013). Situation awareness. *The Oxford handbook of cognitive engineering*, 1:88–108.
- Giorgi, A., Ronca, V., Vozzi, A., Sciaraffa, N., di Florio, A., Tamborra, L., Simonetti, I., Aricó, P., Di Flumeri, G., Rossi, D., and Borghini, G. (2021). Wearable technologies for mental workload, stress, and emotional state assessment during working-like tasks: A comparison with laboratory technologies. *Sensors*, 21(7).
- Hidalgo, C. A., Orghian, D., Canals, J. A., De Almeida, F., and Martin, N. (2021). *How humans judge machines*. MIT Press.
- Hurter, C., Conversy, S., Gianazza, D., and Telea, A. C. (2014). Interactive image-based information visualization for aircraft trajectory analysis. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 47:207–227.
- Isaac, A. R. and Ruitenberg, B. (2017). *Air traffic control: human performance factors*. Routledge.
- Islam, M. R., Ahmed, M. U., Barua, S., and Begum, S. (2022). A systematic review of explainable artificial intelligence in terms of different application domains and tasks. *Applied Sciences - Computing and Artificial Intelligence (Special Issue: Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI))*, pages 1–38.
- Kirwan, B., Flynn, M., and Bretigny, F. (2001). Identification of air traffic controller conflict resolution strategies for the cora (conflict resolution assistant) project. In *Proceedings of the 4th USA/Europe Air Traffic Management R&D Seminar*, pages 3–7.
- Letondal, C., Hurter, C., Lesbordes, R., Vinot, J.-L., and Conversy, S. (2013). Flights in my hands: coherence concerns in designing strip'tic, a tangible space for air traffic controllers. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pages 2175–2184.
- Mackay, W. E. (1999). Is paper safer? the role of paper flight strips in air traffic control. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)*, 6(4):311–340.
- Riche, N. H., Hurter, C., Diakopoulos, N., and Carpendale, S. (2018). *Data-driven storytelling*. CRC Press.
- Scheepens, R., Willems, N., van de Wetering, H., Andrienko, G., Andrienko, N., and van Wijk, J. J. (2011). Composite density maps for multivariate trajectories. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 17(12):2518–2527.
- Srinivas, M. and Patnaik, L. M. (1994). Genetic algorithms: A survey. *computer*, 27(6):17–26.
- Wang, D., Yang, Q., Abdul, A., and Lim, B. Y. (2019). Designing Theory-Driven User-Centric Explainable AI. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - CHI '19*, pages 1–15, New York, New York, USA. ACM Press.
- Westin, C. (2017). Strategic conformance: Exploring acceptance of individual-sensitive automation for air traffic control.